

Tracking and Identification of Distant Missiles by Remote Sounding¹

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Abstract-- Military operations require early warning and identification of theater ballistic missiles (TBM) while they are yet at low altitude. TBMs can operate in vast areas denied to current radar and IR surveillance systems. A form of single sensor or monocular passive ranging (MPR) may make possible TBM tracking in the lower atmosphere from space with simplified, less costly systems utilizing fewer sensors. MPR, a multi-band IR process exploiting atmospheric differential spectral attenuation, has been initially verified by airborne and overhead data. A method, using MPR and trajectory estimation procedures, is described that extracts three dimensional (3D) TBM trajectories.

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1. INTRODUCTION--PASSIVE SENSORS FOR PREDICTING MISSILE IMPACT

Range to military targets is a central need of war operations. Ranging is carried out by a forward observer's trained eye, known landmarks, and optical range finders. Since 1940 radar has greatly advanced ranging performance over long distances in most weathers. Other emitting (active) means use acoustics and laser sources.

Radar, the premier ranging sensor, attracts immense counter measure (CM) efforts. Passive CMs, such as signature modification, vary from cheap chaff to costly stealth aircraft. Active CMs, including anti-radiation missiles (ARM) which home on radar emissions, are proliferating globally. Over 2000 AGM-45 Shrikes and AGM-88 HARMs were used in Operation Desert Storm [1]. All sides

will increasingly use new ARMs, e.g. China's new "AWACS-killer missile" [2]. ARMs will considerably hamper air defense and surveillance radars. Radar life times may be shortened or, at the least, vital radars may be forced "off the air" at crucial moments.

Ranging in XXIst century battlefields that are populated with ARMs will be based on new technologies. One option advances radar electronic measures to cope with intense CM environments. A second pushes R&D for new ranging means. This paper discusses an approach for passive ranging to bright military targets (e.g. missiles, bombs, and fires) by using atmospheric spectral properties. This approach uses monocular passive ranging (MPR) that preserves the geometrical simplicity of active, single sensors while not compromising operation and location.

1.1 Origins of Monocular Passive Ranging

For decades sounding has been used in the analysis of planetary atmospheres. Air density and temperature decrease with altitude while molecular spectral emissivity decreases with temperature. Emitting strata interact to produce the spectral radiance upwelling at the top of an atmosphere. This spectrum can be processed to estimate vertical profiles of temperature, density, and pressure [3].

Overhead, nadir-viewing satellites carrying multi-band radiometers probe the Earth's atmosphere in the 60GHz oxygen line and the 4.3 μ m and 15 μ m carbon dioxide band. It is important that each species be well mixed as in these cases for altitudes up to about 100km. Carbon dioxide lines are used in probing the atmospheres of Venus and Mars while the 7.7 μ m line is used for assessing the fairly uniformly mixed methane of Jupiter's atmosphere.

Multi-band data may also be used to extract the "depth" of a bright point source within an atmosphere. Generally, a viewing line of sight (LOS) has both vertical and side-looking components, Figure 1, and a source may be viewed either from above or within the atmosphere. MPR is the

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application of multi-band processing to passively acquired data from one sensor to the general problem of estimating range along the sensor's LOS to a point source within an atmosphere.

Figure 1 Space sensor viewing geometry with vertical (nadir) and side-looking LOS components [11].

Use of MPR to range to distant TBMs, for which a nearly constant in-band source signature ratio is discussed by Jeffrey et al. [4] for both satellite and aircraft sensors. Earlier passive ranging studies had required either complete knowledge of source spectra or separate rotational lines [5, 6, 7, and 8]. A space-based, nadir-viewing case used many IR radiometer bands and employed neural networks to interpolate altitudes (after "training" based on a limited set of modeled altitudes [9]). MPR is also referred to as the single sensor altitude method [10].

1.2 TBM Threat Impact and MPR

Many military threats are point sources of intense radiation. TBMs that deliver weapons of mass destruction are the focus here. Rocket engines boost TBMs along a trajectory until engine cut-off (ECO). At ECO TBM velocity, acceleration, and location data could be used for early estimates of the warhead ground impact point. A sensor-processor system with an MPR capability, which collects both cross-range and along-range measurements, can report TBM motion as a sequence of 3D positions with errors. Each "error ellipsoid" describes the TBM's 3D position as reported by the sensor within each measurement "frame time". This sequence of 3D locations, given an impact estimation process, could be the basis for predicting TBM impact locations.

1.3 Impact Estimation Process & Timelines

Impact estimation, using MPR sensors for TBM tracking and trajectory estimation, is discussed by Perlman et al. [11,12] and outlined in Figure 2. A sensor, using optimum pass bands, generates frames from which the TBM is extracted, by background suppression processes, and is identified (ID), by spectral, intensity and temporal matching. Range along the LOS is estimated and combined with cross-range data to form the sequence of 3D location error ellipsoids. Combined with a mechanical TBM model, these locations are used by the Impact Prediction by Trajectory Estimation (IPTE) code [13] that predicts TBM impact.

Figure 2. Multi-band sensor cross-track and along-LOS (MPR) results drive trajectory and impact estimation.

A fundamental difference between civilian atmospheric measurement and military TBM reporting is the latter's need for higher data rates and shorter reporting cycles. This is because TBM exhausts may be observable for only 10's of seconds while accurate tracking of TBM events requires ECO timing to 0.1 second or better. Further, processing of MPR data into a useful report must be completed within 5 to 10 seconds of ECO to be useful to defenders.

2. PHYSICS OF PASSIVE RANGING

Geometry is central to MPR estimates. A sensor at r_s above the Earth center views a missile along a LOS at range R_1 through the atmosphere at an elevation angle θ , figure 1. From the missile at height h , the sensor is at zenith angle ϕ (generally is larger than θ due to the Earth's curvature). Atmospheric models define a "top" of the atmosphere at R_2 along the LOS.

Absorption occurs in molecular bands along the path R_1 - R_2 . Atmospheric molecular column density increases in a known way as R_1 increases along the LOS. For a pair of well-chosen bands, the measured band ratio indicates the column density along the LOS. R_1 is found by comparing the two. The CO_2 4.3 μm band offers several benefits. It is largely removed from solar clutter, is minimally affected by "weather" (water vapor and dust variations), and is at a strong emission region for TBMs. Jeffrey et al., [4], after

simplifying assumptions, derive the equations for MPR (their equations 7 and 8, respectively). In sum, the known distribution of CO₂ in the atmosphere provides a standard by which distance can be measured.

A non-closed form range derivation illustrates MPR parameter dependencies, Chuang et al. [14]. Source power, S_i, is seen through an atmosphere of transmissivity τ_i in bands i = 1,2. The missile as a "point" source radiates from a pixel of an area that is range squared times instantaneous field of view (IFOV) solid angle Δω (sr). Behind S_i is a scene background radiance A_{ib}(R) (W/cm²-sr) from the area Δω R². The radiance along the path R is included in A_{ib} in this expression. Scene in-band radiance is A_i (W/cm²-sr):

$$A_i = \frac{S_i}{\Delta\omega R^2} \tau_i + A_{ib}(R), \quad \text{for } i = 1 \& 2 \quad (1)$$

Transmissivity over the path of length R is:

$$\tau_i = e^{-\alpha_0 \int_{R_T}^{R_1} e^{-h/H} dR} \quad (2)$$

Transmissivity is dependent on the altitude of the path R start, R_T, and end, R₁, points and molecular band absorptivity, α₀ (km⁻¹). h (km) is the altitude of the air volume dv at range R₁ and H is atmospheric exponential scale height.

Changing variables from R to R' by R = R₀ - R', where R₀ is the distance from the satellite to the surface of the Earth (see figure 1), τ_i can be written:

$$\tau_i = e^{-\alpha_0 \int_{R_T}^{R_1} e^{-\frac{R \cos \phi}{H}} dR'} \quad (3)$$

where φ is the local zenith angle along the R path and h = R cos φ. The integral for τ_i over R << R₀ (a near "flat earth" case for which φ is taken to be constant) then becomes:

$$\tau_i = e^{-\frac{\alpha_0 H}{\cos \phi} \left[e^{-\frac{R_1 \cos \phi}{H}} - e^{-\frac{R_T \cos \phi}{H}} \right]} \quad (4)$$

To obtain a simple form for range a number of assumptions are made. Source radiance is assumed to be approximated by S_i = τ_i ε Wbb_i(T) where Wbb_i(T) is black body radiance in band i at temperature T and ε is source emissivity at band i. The MPR carbon dioxide bands are closely spaced, e.g. 0.2μm bandwidth from 4.3μm to 4.7μm. For present purposes it is assumed that missile exhausts in the 4.6μm spectral region are nearly opaque so that ε = 1. If background radiation does not pass through the exhaust and neglecting foreground

radiation, then one can take the ratio of the measured radiances in the two bands and reduce it to:

$$\frac{\tau_2}{\tau_1} = e^{-\frac{(\alpha_{02} - \alpha_{01}) H}{\cos \phi} e^{-\frac{R' \cos \phi}{H}}} \quad (5)$$

Solving for range:

$$R = -\frac{H}{\cos \phi} \ln \left[\frac{\cos \phi}{(\alpha_{02} - \alpha_{01}) H} \ln \frac{C}{B} \right] \quad (6)$$

where R = R₀ - R
and h = R cos φ

where the measured and source ratio are: B = A₂/A₁ and C = S₂/S₁.

3. RANGE UNCERTAINTIES

Range estimates are more valuable if uncertainties can be assessed in parallel, Figure 3. Several types of parameter affect measured range [15, 16]:

1 - Atmosphere - (α ₀ , H, climate, ..)
2 - Target - (S _i , S fluctuations, ..)
3 - Background - (land, sea, cloud, ...)
4 - Sensor - (NEI, filter shift time, ..)
5 - Data Reduction - (processing, ..)
6 - Geometry - (h, φ, etc.)

Let f(.,.) represent a continuous range equation with four system parameters, B, C, G, and M. Net range deviation estimates are expressed by a Taylor expansion of the range function with respect to each parameter [15]:

$$\Delta R = \frac{\partial f(.,.)}{\partial B} \Delta B + \frac{\partial f(.,.)}{\partial C} \Delta C + \frac{\partial f(.,.)}{\partial G} \Delta G + \frac{\partial f(.,.)}{\partial M} \Delta M \quad (7)$$

where G = cos φ and M = (α₂ - α₁) H.

Based on σ_h² = E(ΔR²) and assuming no mutual correlation among variables, all correlation terms, such as E(ΔB, ΔC), E(ΔB, ΔG), etc., converge to zero:

$$\sigma_{R'}^2 = \sigma_B^2 + \sigma_C^2 + \sigma_G^2 + \sigma_M^2 \quad (8)$$

Here ΔB, ΔC, ΔG, and ΔM are the deviations from the mean of the measurement, source, geometry, and atmosphere, B_σ, C_σ, G_σ, M_σ respectively.

A. σ_B denotes the measurement related uncertainty for the measured ratio B that is the ratio of the two signals for the two bands. Sensitivity with respect to B is:

$$\frac{df(.,.)}{dB} = \frac{H}{B \cos \varphi \ln(\frac{C}{B})} \quad (9)$$

Measurement uncertainties are affected by dark current (D), foreground noise (F), gain factor (K) and processing errors, e.g. non-simultaneous or delayed sampling and background subtraction residuals, (BS):

Figure 3. Schematic of how range error budgets can be estimated in parallel with measured range

$$\sigma_B^2 = \sigma_D^2 + \sigma_F^2 + \sigma_K^2 + \sigma_{BS}^2 \quad (10)$$

The error budget shows measurement uncertainty is important when signal to noise is small.

- B. σ_c denotes effects of source signature ratio, C, uncertainty. The sensitivity function is:

$$\frac{df(.,.)}{dC} = -\frac{H}{C \cos \varphi \ln(\frac{C}{B})} \quad (11)$$

Uncertainty in C is due to random temporal fluctuations and systematic bias.

- C. σ_c denotes geometry uncertainties. In a space platform, the atmospheric path is specified by the zenith angle:

$$\frac{df(.,.)}{d\varphi} = \tan \varphi \left[f(.,.) + \frac{H}{\cos \varphi} \right] \quad (12)$$

- D. σ_M denotes the atmosphere uncertainties such as in extinction coefficient $D\alpha_0$ and scale height H:

$$\frac{df(.,.)}{dD\alpha_0} = \frac{H}{\cos \varphi D\alpha_0}, \text{ where } D\alpha_0 = (\alpha_{02} - \alpha_{01}) \quad (13)$$

Uncertainties along the path arise due to variations in gas component temperature and density. The uniformity of carbon dioxide mixing keeps these errors relatively low [4]. Variations due to aerosols, dust and water droplets may not be significant. This is because aerosols are broad band spectral absorbers contributing to extinction but negligibly to spectral distortion. As MPR is a spectral method it is weakly affected by aerosols that have broadband features.

Error budgets can be estimated once MPR sensor parameters (e.g. NEI and IFOV) and geometry (i.e. sensor height and elevation angle) are selected. Uncertainty in range for a 20 cm aperture over a 250 km LOS to a typical missile could be on the order of 5%, Chuang et al. [15]. For a missile launch each error varies from launch to ECO.

In Figure 4 range error is shown as a function of R', the range from target to ground, here for a 75° zenith angle. Errors can be reduced by adaptively changing filters (band "agility") [11, 14]. Error curves about the actual range (heavy diagonal) are show for: (1) data associated noise σ_b , (2) source fluctuation σ_c , (3) look angle uncertainty σ_ϕ , and (4) atmospheric coefficient uncertainty σ_{po} . For a fixed filter pair, errors are large at low altitude where attenuation reduces signal and at high altitude where attenuation weakens.

Figure 4. Typical MPR error behavior for a fixed filter pair.

MPR is a spectral method so that band to band calibration is critical while absolute calibration is less so, provided there is sufficient signal. An example of the importance of maintaining spectral calibration is shown for interference filters as their filter characteristics change with temperature so that monitoring filter temperature is critical [15].

4. IMPACT PREDICTION BY TRAJECTORY ESTIMATION

The Impact Prediction by Trajectory Estimation (IPTE) code models 5 phases of missile flight using the equations of motion in their time sequence:

1. The TBM is in vertical flight from $t = 0$ to t_k ;
2. At t_k the TBM "kicks over" to some pitch angle, in a finite time interval, to a "launch azimuth" direction;
3. The TBM then flies at constant pitch angle until the velocity vector is in line with the missile pitch angle;

4. The TBM then flies a "gravity turn" (zero angle of attack) until it reaches a desired pitch angle;
5. The TBM maintains constant pitch until burnout, at which time it enters ballistic coast.

IPTE calculates acceleration resulting from forces acting on the missile - thrust, gravity and drag. Missile flight parameters needed for these calculations, such as the missile weight at launch, fuel burn rate, thrust, cross-section, specific impulse, etc., are available [17].

Acceleration due to gravity is calculated as the gradient of the potential function modeled as an infinite spherical harmonic series given in its most general form as:

$$U = \frac{\mu}{r} \left[1 - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} J_n \left(\frac{a}{r} \right)^n P_n(\sin \phi) - \sum_{n=2, m=2}^{\infty} J_n^m \left(\frac{a}{r} \right)^n P_n^m(\sin \phi) \cos(\lambda - \lambda_n^m) \right] \quad (14)$$

Here m is the Earth mass times the universal gravity constant; a is the mean equatorial radius of the earth. J_n , J_n^m , and λ_n^m are constants of the series which have been determined from least squares fits to satellite observations. $P_n(\sin \phi)$ and $P_n^m(\sin \phi)$ are Legendre polynomials generated from recursive relationships for which the series constants are given [18].

Aerodynamic drag opposes the air relative velocity vector, assuming that lift, an aerodynamic force acting normal to the velocity vector, is negligible. Drag is the product of dynamic pressure, drag coefficient, C_D , and a reference cross-section area, A :

$$A_D = - \frac{\rho V_A^2 C_D A}{2m} \quad (15)$$

Here ρ is air density and m is missile instantaneous mass.

Thrust is individually modeled for each phase of a multi-stage missile. Several physical details are known or estimated for each phase, including total mass, M , at the beginning of the phase, mass burn rate, vacuum specific impulse, I_{sp} , engine exit area, A_E ; and mass jettisoned mass at staging. Thrust acceleration (with no drag) during a boost phase is:

$$A_T = \frac{m \dot{I}_{sp} - P A_E}{M - \dot{m} \Delta t} \quad (16)$$

where P is ambient pressure at h and Δt is phase duration.

Given an initial estimate of trajectory parameters, the IPTE code compares the resulting trajectory estimate with the TBM location sequence. IPTE will then adjust the estimated trajectory until it converges to the location data. Minimum variance estimation equations, a form of the

weighted least square fit, are used to make this match. IPTE considers earth rotation.

Best estimates of TBM trajectory are the basis of launch location, azimuth, ballistic coast and impact. At engine cut-off, estimated state vectors are used as initial conditions for the ballistic phase of the TBM flight ending with reentry drag and prediction of impact.

A simulated impact point prediction, with errors based on detection by an orbiting sensor using MPR and IPTE trajectory estimation, is given by Perlman et al. [12, 19]. A TBM launch observation was simulated in the 4.5 μm band using an overhead sensor with a 1 X 1 km pixel size and only dark current noise. The results, Figure 5, show predicted impact 90% error ellipse probabilities (EEP). Effects of heavy cloud cover on impact point EEP are found by neglecting sensor observations from launch to 10 and 15 km, respectively. Continuous selection of optimum filters may result in even smaller EEPs for launch and impact points as compared with the use of a fixed band pair. These results are better than those for existing, passive, angle-only (stereo viewing) sensors [19].

Figure 5. Simulated impact EEPs for TBM observed from ground (clear sky), 5 km and 10 km cloud break. [19]

5. CONCLUSION - STATUS AND POTENTIAL OF THE MPR/IPTE SYSTEM

Missile trajectory tracking and impact prediction by passive means will become an increasingly important in the severe ARM environment of future battlefields. The MPR/IPTE model for passively reporting missile flight and predicting impact is under study. Validation of MPR ranges against distant missiles is being pursued. Three analyses support the value of MPR ranges (ARGUS data [4], satellite data [20], and ARES data [21]). Verification field programs are under review [22]. Also ongoing are examinations of

potential new defense approaches made possible by MPR/IPTE systems such as boost phase intercepts [23, 24].

For TBM tracking missions the potential value of MPR/IPTE impact prediction is that it uses a single sensor, is fast and passive. TBM impact predictions are quite "perishable" and require responsive transmission over available narrow band comm links to military users. The MPR/IPTE model offers a technologically practical to provide such responsive impact predictions.

Success of MPR applications may bring a number of benefits. TMD impact predictions could be rapidly and covertly reported. Cueing of major ground based (GBR) and airborne radars might proceed using MPR-based data acquired both before and at ECO. Forward located MPR sensor and processing packages, when deployed in large numbers, could send back expected tracks well before the TBM warheads break radar horizons. For both TMD impact prediction and GBR cueing, only one sensor is needed. This means that impact predictions or radar cues can be formulated rapidly at the sensor and be sent directly to defenders.

MPR employs well-understood electro-optical sensors that are small, light, frugal in the use of power, and inexpensive. Satellite constellations might be considerably reduced and simplified. Overall, as battlefields become more dangerous for radar a family of covert, high-speed reporting MPR-based ranging systems may emerge to complement and support radar.

6. GLOSSARY

A	reference cross-section
A_D	drag
A_E	engine exit area
A_i	apparent radiance of plume, in $\text{W}/\text{cm}^2\text{-sr}$
ΔA_i	incremental in-band radiance, the AC term of A_i
α_o	atmospheric extinction coefficient at $h = 0$, in km^{-1}
B_{ij}	in-band radiance ratio of band i and band j
ΔB_{ij}	incremental in-band ratio
BS	background subtraction residual
C_{ij}	in-band source ratio between band i and band j
C_D	drag coefficient
D	dark current
$\Delta \alpha_o$	α_o difference between band i and band j
ECO	engine cut-off
EEP	error ellipse of probability
$f(.,.)$	range equation function
F	foreground noise
FOV	field of view
GBR	ground based radar
h	target altitude, in km
h_s	sensor altitude, in km
H	air density scale height, in km

<i>IFOV</i>	instantaneous FOV
I_{sp}	propellant specific impulse
<i>K</i>	gain factor for non-uniform correction
<i>LOS</i>	line of sight
<i>M</i>	stage initial mass
\dot{m}	mass flow rate
<i>MPR</i>	monocular passive ranging
ϕ	target zenith angle between LOS and local normal
R_t	range from sensor to model "top" of the atmosphere
R_o	LOS ground intercepting range, in km
R_s	target range from sensor, in km
R'	target to ground range, in km
$R = R_t - R_s$	slant range in atmosphere, in km
$\sigma_x^2 = E[\epsilon_x^2]$	variance of ϵ
<i>TBM</i>	theater ballistic missile
τ_i	LOS transmission in band I
t_k	TBM kickover time at boost phase
θ	sensor look angle between LOS and local vertical
V_A	flight speed

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non cooperative target identification (NCTI) and communication networks. At KTAADN he has developed IR sensing and NCTI techniques. Prior to employment at KTAADN, Mr. Perlman was Deputy Director of Engineering with GTE Government Systems, Communication Systems Division and Chief Systems Engineer/Group Leader at the MITRE Corporation. Sumner Perlman has a BS in Electrical Engineering from Virginia Tech and an MS in EE from Northeastern University.

VIII. BIOGRAPHIES

Dr. James Draper, President of KTAADN, is an authority on military weapons signatures, surveillance systems and ordnance use assessment. From 1979 to 1998 he has supported the definition, assessment and planning for COBRA BRASS, an advanced, space-based, multi-spectral, staring sensor. He has led in the development of the USA BOA and related MPR programs and algorithms and their theater missile defense applications. He has carried out electrophilic effectiveness measurements in shock tubes, confirmed the production of partial inversions in CO in NE/MHD channels, measured and developed near-field IR boundary layer noise models for supersonic recce aircraft, analyzed RCS boundary layers and wakes using KREMS data, modeled high-altitude rocket plume hypersonic scaling relations and nomograms, developed rocket plume radiation and RCS signatures, assessed sea skimming cruise missile RCS wakes, developed overhead systems for monitoring ordnance situational awareness, and participated in building remote gust mappers for America Cup racers. He received his PhD in Aero/Astro at MIT in 1971.

Mr. Sumner Perlman is an electrical engineer with experience in many phases of system engineering. This included design, simulation and analysis of remote passive ranging, theater missile defense, radar systems,

Dr. Chiu-Kuang Chuang of KTAADN is lead investigator for MPR technology. He has built MPR algorithms and applied them to range error assessment, air borne and space borne design and data analyses. Recently he conducted an in-depth sensor trade study to explore the MPR application potential of advanced photodetector technologies, developed under BMDO and DARPA. He received his B.S., M.S and Ph.D. in Electrical and Communication Engineer all from Tohoku University, Sendai, Japan, 1972.

Mr. Matthew Hanson recently joined KTAADN as a Software Engineer where he has been writing and developing code and acting as computer administrator. Code development is for signal and image processing applications such as MPR or display projects. Previously, he worked at Dolan-Jenner Industries as an Applications Engineer, providing technical support for fiber optics and machine vision industrial applications. At the Laboratory for Laser Energetics, Mr. Hanson aided in the creation of phase plates and the Target Viewing System for the Omega Laser system, used for research in inertial fusion. Mr. Hanson received his BS in Imaging and Photographic Technology at the Rochester Institute of Technology in 1995.

Mr. Larry Lillard is a senior aerospace engineer and is president and founder of SMRT, Inc., a small consulting firm providing analytical support and training for both government and industry. He spent a distinguished career as a federal employee at the Air Force Foreign Technology Division (FTD) from

1967 to 1994. He has a BS degree in mathematics and MS degrees in engineering from the University of Illinois (1996) and the Air Force Institute of Technology (1982). Mr. Lillard is an expert in optimal estimation techniques, flight mechanics of ballistic missiles, and FORTRAN programming. He specializes in developing code for estimation the trajectories of space and missile systems from data collected from various types of sensors, radar, optical and IR, during all phases of flight

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